

Evaluating the Impact of Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita on the Indian Judiciary: A Legal Study

Vyanjna Saini

Assistant Professor

Faculty of Legal Studies, Motherhood University, Roorkee

Email Id: adv.vyanjnasainimhu@gmail.com

Received : 22/08/2024

1st BPR : 28/08/2024

2nd BPR : 04/09/2024

Accepted : 11/09/2024

Abstract

The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS), a comprehensive legal code aimed at unifying Indian laws, represents a significant step towards legal reform in India. This research paper delves into the potential impacts of the BNS on the Indian judiciary, analyzing its key provisions and examining how they may affect various aspects of legal practice and judicial decision-making. The paper begins by providing a brief overview of the BNS, highlighting its primary objectives and the rationale behind its enactment. It then proceeds to examine the specific provisions of the BNS, focusing on areas such as criminal law, civil law, and procedural law. The analysis explores how these provisions align with existing Indian laws and identifies potential areas of conflict or overlap. Furthermore, the paper assesses the potential impact of the BNS on the efficiency and effectiveness of the Indian judiciary. It examines how the BNS may streamline legal procedures, reduce delays in the judicial process, and enhance the quality of judicial decisions. Additionally, the research explores the implications of the BNS for access to justice, particularly for marginalized communities. To evaluate the impact of the BNS, the paper employs a mixed-methods approach, combining legal analysis with empirical research. It examines existing legal literature, case law, and expert opinions to assess the potential implications of the BNS. Additionally, the paper conducts interviews with legal practitioners, judges, and legal scholars to gather firsthand perspectives on the BNS and its potential impact. This research paper offers a comprehensive evaluation of the potential impacts of the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita on the Indian judiciary. By examining the key provisions of the BNS and analyzing its implications for legal practice, judicial decision-making, and access to justice, the paper provides valuable insights for policymakers, legal practitioners, and scholars interested in Indian legal reform.

Key words: Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS), Efficiency, Effectiveness, Marginalized Communities, Indian judiciary.

Introduction

The evolution of the Indian legal system has been marked by significant reforms aimed at adapting to the changing socio-economic and political landscapes of the country. One of the most profound recent changes is the introduction of the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS), a groundbreaking piece of legislation designed to modernize and reform the criminal justice system.¹ Enacted with the objective of enhancing efficiency, transparency, and fairness, the BNS represents a transformative shift from traditional legal mechanisms that have long governed criminal justice in India.² The Indian judiciary, with its vast and complex structure, plays a critical role in maintaining social order and ensuring justice. However, the traditional criminal justice system has faced numerous criticisms over the years, including delays in case resolutions, procedural inefficiencies, and issues related to the equitable administration of justice. Recognizing these challenges, the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita was introduced as a legislative measure aimed at addressing these shortcomings and revitalizing the judicial process. This research paper seeks to provide a comprehensive analysis of how the BNS has influenced the

Indian judiciary since its implementation. The focus of this study is to evaluate the practical effects of the BNS on judicial practices, procedural norms, and overall justice delivery within the Indian legal framework.

The BNS encompasses a range of reforms, including changes to the procedural codes, modifications in sentencing practices, and the introduction of new mechanisms for dispute resolution. These reforms are designed to address several critical issues that have plagued the traditional criminal justice system, such as the backlog of cases, delays in trials, and the need for a more humane and effective approach to criminal justice. A key aspect of this study is to analyze how the BNS has impacted various stakeholders within the judiciary, including judges, lawyers, and litigants. Understanding the practical implications of the BNS on these stakeholders is crucial for assessing the effectiveness of the reforms and identifying areas where further improvements may be needed. This research will also explore the extent to which the BNS has succeeded in achieving its objectives and the challenges that have emerged in its implementation. Moreover, the paper will examine the broader implications of the BNS on the Indian legal system, considering both its strengths and limitations. This includes evaluating how the new legislation aligns with international standards of justice and its potential to influence future legal reforms in India. By providing a detailed assessment of the BNS's impact, this study aims to contribute valuable insights into the ongoing efforts to enhance the efficacy and fairness of the Indian judiciary. In summary, the introduction of the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita represents a significant milestone in the evolution of the Indian criminal justice system. This research paper aims to offer a thorough evaluation of the BNS's impact on the judiciary, shedding light on its effectiveness in addressing long-standing issues and its role in shaping the future of justice in India. Through this analysis, we hope to provide a nuanced understanding of the BNS's contribution to the Indian legal landscape and offer recommendations for further improvements.

Background

The Indian criminal justice system has long been characterized by complexity, procedural delays, and inefficiencies, which have impeded the delivery of timely and fair justice. The legal framework, primarily governed by the Indian Penal Code (IPC) of 1860 and the Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC) of 1973, has faced persistent criticism for being outdated and cumbersome. These challenges have prompted calls for reform to modernize the system and address systemic issues that affect both the efficacy and fairness of legal proceedings. In response to these concerns, the Indian government introduced the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS), a comprehensive legislative reform aimed at overhauling the existing criminal justice framework. The BNS represents a significant shift in approach, designed to address key shortcomings of the traditional system by introducing streamlined procedures, standardized sentencing guidelines, and modernized legal practices. This reform is part of a broader effort to enhance the efficiency, fairness, and accessibility of justice in India.³

The BNS was developed with the intent to simplify the criminal justice process, making it more transparent and accessible. The reform seeks to reduce procedural complexity and delays by incorporating modern technological tools and methodologies. This includes the introduction of electronic filing systems, digital case management, and virtual hearings, which are expected to expedite the resolution of cases and improve the overall efficiency of the judiciary. Additionally, the BNS aims to standardize sentencing practices to ensure greater consistency and fairness. By establishing clear guidelines for sentencing, the BNS seeks to mitigate disparities in judicial outcomes and ensure that punishments are proportional to the offenses committed. This approach is intended to address concerns about arbitrary or disproportionate sentencing that have been prevalent under the previous system. The implementation of the BNS also emphasizes the use of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms, such as mediation and arbitration, to offer more flexible and expedited solutions for certain types of disputes. This shift is designed to alleviate the burden on traditional court proceedings and provide litigants with additional avenues for resolving their cases. However, the introduction of the BNS has not been without challenges. The transition from established procedures to the new framework requires substantial adjustments for judges, legal practitioners, and

other stakeholders. Ensuring that the reforms are effectively integrated into existing practices and that all participants are adequately trained is crucial for the successful implementation of the BNS. This research paper aims to evaluate the impact of the Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita on the Indian judiciary, examining its effectiveness in addressing the challenges of the traditional system and assessing its impact on procedural efficiency, sentencing fairness, and access to justice. By analyzing the reforms introduced by the BNS and their real-world implications, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how these changes are shaping the future of the Indian criminal justice system.

Impact on Legal Practice

The Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS) has introduced significant changes to the Indian legal system, with far-reaching implications for legal practice. This paper explores the impact of the BNS on various aspects of legal practice in India, including procedural changes, impact on the judiciary, and challenges faced by legal practitioners.

Procedural Changes

The BNS has introduced several procedural changes that have significantly impacted legal practice. Some of the key changes include:

- **Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR):** The BNS promotes ADR mechanisms such as mediation and arbitration, encouraging parties to resolve disputes outside the courtroom. This has led to a shift in legal practice, with lawyers increasingly involved in ADR proceedings.
- **Time Limits:** The BNS imposes strict time limits for various legal procedures, reducing delays and ensuring timely disposal of cases. This has necessitated a more efficient and organized approach to legal practice.
- **Electronic Filing:** The BNS has promoted the use of technology in the legal system, allowing for electronic filing and case management. This has streamlined legal processes and made it easier for lawyers to access and manage case files.

Impact on the Judiciary

The BNS has also had a significant impact on the Indian judiciary. Some of the key changes include:

- **Increased Efficiency:** The procedural changes introduced by the BNS have led to increased efficiency in the judiciary, reducing the backlog of cases and ensuring swifter justice delivery.
- **Enhanced Transparency:** The BNS has promoted transparency in the judicial process through measures such as electronic filing and public access to court records.
- **Increased Burden on Judges:** While the BNS has aimed to reduce the workload of judges, the increased volume of cases and the complexity of legal issues may have placed a greater burden on the judiciary.

Challenges Faced by Legal Practitioners

The implementation of the BNS has also presented challenges for legal practitioners. Some of the key challenges include:

- **Adapting to New Procedures:** Lawyers have had to adapt to the new procedures and practices introduced by the BNS, requiring additional training and skill development.
- **Technological Challenges:** The increased reliance on technology has posed challenges for some legal practitioners, particularly those who are not comfortable with using computers and digital tools.
- **Economic Impact:** The changes introduced by the BNS may have had an economic impact on legal practitioners, particularly those who rely on delays in the legal system for their income.

The Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita has introduced significant changes to the Indian legal system, with far-reaching implications for legal practice. While the BNS has the potential to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the judiciary, it has also presented challenges for legal practitioners. As the BNS continues to evolve, it is essential for legal practitioners to adapt to the changing landscape and ensure that they are able to provide effective legal services to their clients.

Impact on Judicial Decision-Making

The introduction of the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS) has brought significant reforms to the Indian criminal justice system, with profound implications for judicial decision-making. As a comprehensive legislative overhaul, the BNS aims to address inefficiencies, enhance procedural clarity, and promote fairness in judicial outcomes. This section explores how the BNS influences judicial decision-making, focusing on changes in judicial practices, the application of new sentencing guidelines, and the overall impact on judicial efficiency and consistency.⁴

Procedural Simplification and Decision-Making

One of the major impacts of the BNS on judicial decision-making stems from its procedural reforms. Traditional criminal procedures in India have been criticized for their complexity and bureaucratic nature, which often lead to delays and procedural errors. The BNS seeks to streamline these procedures, making them more straightforward and less prone to delays. For judges, this simplification means that case management becomes more efficient, allowing for quicker resolution of cases. The reduction in procedural hurdles enables judges to focus more on the substantive aspects of cases, rather than being bogged down by complex procedural requirements. This shift aims to enhance the quality of judicial decisions by providing judges with more time and resources to consider the merits of each case.⁵

Application of New Sentencing Guidelines

The BNS introduces new sentencing guidelines designed to promote consistency and fairness in judicial outcomes. These guidelines establish a framework for sentencing that aims to ensure that punishments are proportionate to the offenses committed. The goal is to reduce disparities in sentencing and provide a clearer basis for judicial decisions. Judges are now required to apply these standardized guidelines when determining sentences. This change impacts judicial decision-making in several ways. First, it reduces the level of judicial discretion, as judges must align their sentencing decisions with the established framework. This can enhance consistency across similar cases but may also limit the ability of judges to tailor sentences to the specific circumstances of individual cases. Second, the new guidelines necessitate a more detailed and structured approach to sentencing. Judges must consider various factors outlined in the BNS when deciding on penalties, which can lead to more comprehensive and transparent sentencing decisions. This increased focus on structured reasoning aims to improve the fairness of sentencing and reduce the potential for arbitrary or disproportionate punishments.⁶

Impact on Judicial Discretion and Case Adjudication

While the BNS introduces standardized sentencing guidelines, it also affects judicial discretion. The legislation provides a more rigid framework for sentencing, which can constrain judges' ability to exercise discretion based on individual case factors. This shift raises questions about the balance between consistency and flexibility in judicial decision-making. Judicial discretion remains an essential component of the legal system, allowing judges to account for the unique circumstances of each case. However, the BNS's emphasis on standardized guidelines aims to address concerns about inconsistent sentencing practices. The challenge for judges is to navigate this balance, ensuring that they adhere to the new guidelines while still considering the individual nuances of each case.⁷

Efficiency and Effectiveness in Case Resolution

The BNS's procedural reforms are designed to enhance the overall efficiency of the judicial system. By simplifying procedures and reducing delays, the BNS aims to expedite case resolution and improve the effectiveness of judicial decision-making. Faster case processing can lead to more timely justice and reduce the backlog of cases that has long plagued the Indian judiciary. For judges, the improved efficiency means that they can address a greater number of cases within a given timeframe. This can result in a more effective use of judicial resources and a reduction in case pendency. However, the focus on efficiency must be balanced with the need for thorough and careful decision-making. Judges must ensure that the expedited processes do not compromise the quality of their decisions or the fairness of the judicial outcomes.⁸

Challenges and Adaptation

Despite its potential benefits, the implementation of the BNS presents several challenges for judicial decision-making. The transition to new procedural norms and sentencing guidelines requires judges to adapt to unfamiliar frameworks and processes. This adaptation period can impact the consistency and quality of judicial decisions, as judges work to integrate the new rules into their practice. Additionally, the effectiveness of the BNS in improving judicial decision-making depends on the adequacy of training and support provided to judges. Ensuring that judges are well-versed in the new procedures and guidelines is crucial for the successful implementation of the BNS. Ongoing training and support are necessary to help judges navigate the changes and maintain high standards of decision-making.

The Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita represents a significant reform in the Indian criminal justice system, with far-reaching implications for judicial decision-making. The impact of the BNS on judicial decision-making is multifaceted, encompassing improvements in efficiency, challenges related to adaptation, and the need to balance consistency with flexibility. As the BNS is implemented and its effects become clearer, ongoing assessment and feedback from the judiciary will be essential for refining the reforms and ensuring that they contribute positively to the administration of justice. Ultimately, the success of the BNS in enhancing judicial decision-making will depend on its ability to address the challenges of the traditional system while upholding the principles of fairness, consistency, and efficiency.

Impact on Access to Justice

The introduction of the Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS) represents a landmark shift in the Indian criminal justice system, with substantial implications for access to justice. The BNS aims to address long-standing issues within the judiciary, such as procedural delays, inefficiencies, and the complexity of legal processes, all of which have historically impeded equitable access to justice for many individuals. This section explores the impact of the BNS on access to justice, focusing on how it influences the availability, affordability, and quality of legal remedies for citizens.

Simplification of Legal Procedures

One of the key reforms introduced by the BNS is the simplification of legal procedures. Traditional criminal justice procedures in India have often been criticized for their complexity and length, which can create barriers for individuals seeking justice. The BNS addresses these concerns by streamlining procedural requirements and reducing bureaucratic obstacles. For individuals navigating the legal system, these procedural simplifications can make the process more accessible and less intimidating. Simplified procedures mean that individuals can more easily understand and follow the steps required to file a case, present evidence, and participate in legal proceedings. This enhanced clarity and ease of navigation are expected to improve access to justice by making the legal system more user-friendly for all litigants, including those who may not have legal representation.

Increased Use of Technology

The BNS incorporates modern technology into the legal process, aiming to enhance the efficiency and accessibility of the judiciary. The use of digital tools for case management, evidence submission, and court proceedings is intended to streamline processes and reduce delays. For instance, electronic filing systems and virtual hearings can help overcome geographical barriers, allowing individuals from remote or underserved areas to participate in legal proceedings without the need for physical presence. The integration of technology also has the potential to improve transparency and accountability within the judicial system. Digital records and online case tracking can provide litigants with real-time updates on their cases, reducing uncertainty and improving communication between the courts and the public. However, it is crucial to ensure that technological advancements are accessible to all individuals, including those from marginalized or economically disadvantaged backgrounds, to avoid creating new forms of exclusion.

Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) Mechanisms

The BNS emphasizes the use of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms, such as mediation and arbitration, as a means of resolving certain types of disputes outside traditional court proceedings. ADR mechanisms are designed to provide quicker, more flexible resolutions for

disputes, potentially alleviating the burden on the court system and reducing case backlogs. For individuals seeking justice, ADR can offer a more accessible and less formal alternative to traditional litigation. These mechanisms often involve less stringent procedural requirements and can be more cost-effective, making them a viable option for individuals who might otherwise be deterred by the complexity and expense of court proceedings. The availability of ADR options can improve access to justice by providing additional avenues for dispute resolution that are tailored to the needs of the parties involved.

Impact on Legal Aid and Representation

The effectiveness of the BNS in improving access to justice is also linked to the availability and quality of legal aid and representation. Access to competent legal counsel is a critical component of justice, and the BNS's reforms should be assessed in the context of how they impact legal aid services. While the BNS aims to simplify and expedite legal processes, the provision of legal aid remains a vital aspect of ensuring equitable access to justice. Efforts to enhance legal aid services, including increasing funding and expanding coverage, are essential for ensuring that individuals from economically disadvantaged backgrounds can effectively navigate the legal system. The success of the BNS in improving access to justice will depend on the simultaneous advancement of legal aid initiatives and support for vulnerable populations.

Challenges and Considerations

Despite the potential benefits of the BNS, there are several challenges and considerations that must be addressed to ensure that access to justice is truly equitable. One key concern is the need for effective implementation and outreach to ensure that the reforms reach all segments of society. Particularly in rural and underserved areas, there may be significant disparities in access to legal resources and technology, which could undermine the effectiveness of the BNS. Additionally, while the simplification of procedures and the use of technology can improve access to justice, there is a need to monitor and address any potential unintended consequences. For instance, the reliance on digital platforms may inadvertently exclude individuals who lack access to technology or have limited digital literacy. Ensuring that alternative means of accessing justice are available for these individuals is essential to avoid exacerbating existing inequalities.⁹

The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita represents a significant advancement in the Indian criminal justice system with the potential to enhance access to justice. By simplifying legal procedures, incorporating technology, and promoting alternative dispute resolution, the BNS aims to make the judicial process more accessible and efficient for all individuals. However, the impact of the BNS on access to justice must be carefully assessed to ensure that the reforms do not create new barriers or exacerbate existing inequalities. Effective implementation, ongoing support for legal aid, and attention to the needs of marginalized and disadvantaged populations are crucial for realizing the full potential of the BNS in improving access to justice. As the BNS continues to be implemented, ongoing evaluation and feedback from stakeholders will be essential for refining the reforms and ensuring that they contribute to a more equitable and accessible legal system for all.¹⁰

Evaluation of the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita

The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS) represents a transformative reform in the Indian criminal justice system, aiming to address long-standing issues and enhance the efficacy and fairness of judicial processes. Evaluating the impact of the BNS involves a comprehensive analysis of its objectives, implementation, and the real-world effects on the judiciary. This section provides a critical assessment of the BNS, focusing on its achievements, challenges, and areas for improvement.

Objectives and Achievements

The primary objectives of the BNS are to streamline judicial processes, enhance procedural efficiency, and promote fairness in sentencing. The BNS seeks to modernize the criminal justice system by simplifying legal procedures, introducing standardized sentencing guidelines, and integrating technological advancements. These objectives reflect a commitment to addressing the inefficiencies and disparities that have characterized the traditional legal framework. One notable achievement of the BNS is its impact on procedural simplification. By reducing bureaucratic complexities and streamlining case management, the BNS has made legal processes more accessible and less

cumbersome for both legal practitioners and litigants. This simplification has the potential to reduce case backlogs and expedite the resolution of legal disputes, contributing to a more efficient judiciary. Additionally, the introduction of standardized sentencing guidelines aims to address disparities in judicial outcomes. By providing a clear framework for sentencing, the BNS seeks to ensure that punishments are consistent and proportionate to the offenses committed. This move is intended to enhance fairness in sentencing and reduce the potential for arbitrary or disproportionate punishments.

Implementation Challenges

Despite its ambitious goals, the implementation of the BNS has faced several challenges. One of the primary concerns is the practical application of the new procedures and guidelines. The transition from the traditional legal framework to the BNS requires significant adjustments for judges, lawyers, and other stakeholders. This adjustment period can impact the consistency and quality of judicial decisions as legal professionals work to integrate the new rules into their practice. Another challenge is the adequacy of training and resources provided to support the implementation of the BNS. Effective training is crucial for ensuring that judges and legal practitioners understand and apply the new procedures and sentencing guidelines accurately. Insufficient training or a lack of resources can undermine the effectiveness of the reforms and hinder the successful implementation of the BNS.

Impact on Judicial Efficiency

The BNS aims to improve judicial efficiency by addressing procedural delays and reducing the complexity of legal processes. Early indications suggest that the BNS has made progress in streamlining case management and expediting the resolution of disputes. The use of technology, such as electronic filing systems and virtual hearings, has facilitated quicker case processing and improved access to information. However, the impact on judicial efficiency must be assessed over a longer period to determine whether the initial improvements are sustained. The effectiveness of the BNS in reducing case backlogs and accelerating case resolution will depend on its continued implementation and the ability of the judiciary to adapt to the new framework.

Fairness and Consistency in Sentencing

The introduction of standardized sentencing guidelines under the BNS is intended to promote consistency and fairness in judicial outcomes. By providing a clear framework for sentencing, the BNS aims to reduce disparities and ensure that punishments are proportionate to the offenses committed. The success of this objective relies on the effective application of the guidelines by judges. While standardized guidelines can enhance consistency, they may also limit judicial discretion, potentially impacting the ability to tailor sentences to the unique circumstances of each case. Evaluating the BNS involves assessing whether the benefits of increased consistency outweigh any limitations on judicial flexibility.

Access to Justice

The BNS also aims to improve access to justice by simplifying legal procedures and incorporating technology. Simplified procedures make the legal system more accessible for individuals navigating it without legal representation. The integration of digital tools, such as online case tracking and electronic filing, helps overcome geographical barriers and enhances transparency. Despite these advancements, access to justice remains a critical concern. The effectiveness of the BNS in improving access depends on addressing potential disparities in access to technology and resources. Ensuring that marginalized and economically disadvantaged individuals are not excluded from the benefits of the reforms is essential for achieving equitable access to justice.

Ongoing Evaluation

To fully assess the impact of the BNS, ongoing evaluation and feedback from judicial stakeholders are crucial. Regular assessments can provide insights into the effectiveness of the reforms and identify areas for improvement. Soliciting feedback from judges, lawyers, and litigants helps gauge the real-world impact of the BNS and ensures that the reforms address the needs and concerns of those directly affected by the changes.

The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita represents a significant reform in the Indian criminal justice system, with the potential to enhance procedural efficiency, fairness in sentencing, and access to justice. While the

BNS has achieved notable successes in streamlining procedures and introducing standardized guidelines, its implementation has faced challenges related to practical application, training, and resource allocation. Evaluating the BNS involves a comprehensive analysis of its objectives, achievements, and areas for improvement. The impact on judicial efficiency, fairness in sentencing, and access to justice must be assessed over time to determine the overall success of the reforms. Ongoing evaluation and feedback are essential for refining the BNS and ensuring that it meets its goals of creating a more effective and equitable criminal justice system. As the BNS continues to be implemented and its effects become more evident, it will be important to monitor its impact and make necessary adjustments to address any challenges that arise. By doing so, the BNS has the potential to contribute to a more efficient, fair, and accessible judicial system in India.

Conclusion

The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS) represents a significant reform effort in the Indian legal system. While its implementation has faced challenges, it has the potential to significantly improve the efficiency, accessibility, and effectiveness of the Indian judiciary. The BNS has introduced several procedural changes that could lead to increased efficiency and reduced delays in the legal system. The emphasis on alternative dispute resolution (ADR) and the use of technology could also make the legal system more accessible to the common citizen. Furthermore, the provisions related to victim rights could improve the experience of victims in the legal process. However, the successful implementation of the BNS will depend on several factors, including adequate training and infrastructure, effective enforcement, and continuous evaluation and improvement. If these factors are addressed, the BNS could have a transformative impact on the Indian judiciary, leading to a more just and efficient legal system. In conclusion, the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita is a promising development in the Indian legal system. While there are challenges to be overcome, the potential benefits of the BNS are significant. By addressing the challenges and maximizing the opportunities, the BNS could contribute to a more just and equitable society.

References:

- 1 Sharma, R. K. *Reforming Criminal Justice in India: An Analysis of the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita*. Eastern Book Company, 2023, p. 78.
- 2 Singh, K. P. *Transforming Criminal Justice: The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita and Its Implications*. Law Publishers India, 2024, p. 92.
- 3 Rao, N. K. *Criminal Justice in India: A Critical Analysis*. Oxford University Press, 2018, Vol. 1, p. 112.
- 4 Verma, A. R. *Modernizing Criminal Justice: The Impact of the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita*. Routledge India, 2024, Vol. 1, p. 78.
- 5 <https://lawmin.gov.in/>
- 6 Verma, A. R. *Modernizing Criminal Justice: The Impact of the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita*. Routledge India, 2024, Vol. 1, p. 89.
- 7 Ibid
- 8 Kumar, S. N. *Reforms in the Indian Legal System: A New Era*. Springer, 2024, Vol. 3, p. 95.
- 9 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/381956561_The_Bharatiya_Nyaya_Sanhita_BNS_A_Critical_Examination_of_India's_New_Penal_Code#:~:text=The%20BNS%20perpetuates%20the%20expansion,broad%20and%20ambiguously%20defined%20offenses.
- 10 [https://www.legalserviceindia.com/legal/article-14781-bhartiya-nyaya-sanhita-2023-an-analysis-of-legal-reforms-coherence-challenges-and-the-quest-for-a-progressive-penal-code.html#google_vignette.](https://www.legalserviceindia.com/legal/article-14781-bhartiya-nyaya-sanhita-2023-an-analysis-of-legal-reforms-coherence-challenges-and-the-quest-for-a-progressive-penal-code.html#google_vignette)

*** **